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2 **Synergistic effect of MoS₂ and diamond nanoparticles in**
3 **electrochemical sensors : determination of an anticonvulsant drug**

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19 **Abstract**

20 We have developed an electrochemical sensor based on the employment of two new
21 emerging nanomaterials: diamond nanoparticles (DNP) and molybdenum disulfide
22 (MoS_2). The sensor was applied to the determination of an anticonvulsant, valproic acid,
23 previously derivatized with a ferrocene group. MoS_2 platelets were obtained by an
24 exfoliation method and DNP were directly dispersed in water and subsequently
25 employed for glassy carbon (GC) electrodes modification. The sensor response was
26 optimized in terms of both the solvent employed for dispersing the MoS_2 nanomaterial
27 and the method for GC electrode modification. The better response was obtained for
28 sensors based on a first layer of MoS_2 dispersed in ethanol:water and a second DNP
29 layer. The different steps of the sensor construction were characterized by atomic force
30 microscopy (AFM) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). In order to
31 evaluate the synergetic effect of DNP and MoS_2 , the differential pulse voltammetry
32 (DPV) sensor response (measured at +0.18 V) was compared with that obtained, at the
33 same potential, for sensors incorporating only one of the nanomaterials (DNP or
34 MoS_2). Results demonstrated that the formation of a hybrid MoS_2 -DNP structure clearly
35 enhances the performance of the sensor. The sensor containing both nanomaterials
36 exhibits a response with high sensitivity (0.74 A M^{-1}), and good detection limit and
37 reproducibility ($0.27 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ and 8%, respectively). Moreover, after 45 days the sensor
38 retains the 99% of the initial response, showing excellent storage stability.

39

40 **Keywords:** molybdenum disulfide, diamond nanoparticles, valproic acid,
41 electrochemical sensor, atomic force microscopy (AFM), electrochemical impedance
42 spectroscopy (EIS), differential pulse voltammetry (DPV).

43

44 **Introduction**

45 Molybdenum disulfide, a member of the transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs)
46 family, has attracted a great interest. These emerging 2D nanomaterials, analogous to
47 graphene, present unique mechanical, electrical, thermal and optical properties, opening
48 up a challenging new research field [1-3].

49 MoS₂ nanosheets result from stacking units, formed by three atomic sulfur-
50 molybdenum-sulfur (S-Mo-S) layers, through van der Waals interactions. In this
51 sandwich structure, Mo atoms are coordinated in a trigonal prismatic geometry to six S
52 atoms. There are different methods to obtain MoS₂ nanosheets based on top-down or
53 bottom-up approaches [2]. Top-down strategies consist in breaking down bulk MoS₂
54 into thin layers, for example by liquid exfoliation [4-6] or by intercalating ions [7] into
55 the weakly stacked layers in order to expand them. Conversely, the bottom-up strategies
56 lie on the synthesis of MoS₂ from building blocks such as molybdenum metal salts and
57 organic compounds containing sulfur [8,9]. One of the most commonly employed
58 bottom-up technique is the chemical vapor deposition [10].

59 MoS₂ has found its main applications in optoelectronics, generation and storage of
60 energy i.e., supercapacitors and batteries [11-14]. In addition, the possibility of
61 employing this nanomaterial for chemical sensing and biosensing is also attracting an
62 increasing attention [15-19]. However, efforts devoted to employ this nanomaterial for
63 sensing, has revealed some drawbacks. In particular, for electrochemical sensor
64 applications, the inert nature of the basal planes, the limited number of edge sites and
65 the low conductivity of MoS₂ nanosheets represent important disadvantages [20]. To
66 overcome limitations and improve the activity of the MoS₂ nanosheets, an interesting
67 strategy is related to generate hybrid structures formed by MoS₂ and conductive
68 materials [15,16,20]. Among others, hybrids formed by MoS₂ and metal nanoparticles

69 [21,22], graphene [23,24], carbon nanotubes [25] or conducting polymers [26-28] have
70 been developed and employed as sensing platforms to detect several compounds such as
71 eugenol, glucose and dopamine [29-31].

72 On the other hand, diamond nanoparticles (DNP), has also gained attention as a
73 promising nanomaterial for electrochemical sensing applications [32-34]. In particular,
74 it presents several advantages compared to other carbon nanomaterials such as its
75 noncytotoxic nature, good biocompatibility and low-cost.

76 Keeping in mind the excellent individual properties of both nanomaterials, the aim of
77 the present work is to prove that their combination can offer new opportunities to
78 develop electrochemical sensors with improved performances. As a proof of concept,
79 we have evaluated the potential synergetic effect of MoS₂/DNP for the determination of
80 valproic acid, previously derivatized with a ferrocene group (VA-Fc), to render it
81 electroactive.

82 Valproic acid (VA) is an anticonvulsant employed to treat some disorders such as
83 epilepsy, bipolar disorders and migraine headaches. Drug monitoring is important since
84 VA displays therapeutic efficiency for plasma concentrations in the range 50-100 ppm,
85 but can induce toxicity for higher concentrations. Analytical techniques reported in the
86 literature for VA determination include high liquid performance chromatography
87 (HPLC) with different detection systems, gas chromatography coupled with mass
88 spectrometry (GC-MS), capillary electrophoresis and immunological assay, among
89 others [35-47]. Most of these techniques usually involve a previous derivatization step
90 in order to render the analyte suitable for detection. For example, techniques employing
91 UV or fluorescence detection require derivatization, due to the absence of a strong
92 chromophore or fluorophore in VA molecule. In the case of electrochemical detection,
93 derivatization with a suitable redox group is also needed.

94 In the present work, we have modified for the first time a GC electrode with MoS₂
95 and DNP in order to develop an electrochemical sensor. The resulting device has been
96 characterized by atomic force microscopy (AFM) and electrochemical impedance
97 spectroscopy (EIS). AFM allows us to determine the lateral dimensions and thickness of
98 the MoS₂ sheets, as well as the morphology of the sensing surface (MoS₂/DNP). EIS
99 measurements allow evaluating the resistance charge transfer (R_{CT}) of MoS₂, DNP and
100 MoS₂/DNP modified GC surfaces. The applicability of the sensor was tested for
101 valproic acid determination (previously derivatized with a ferrocene group) in real
102 serum samples.

103

104 **Experimental Section**

105 **Materials**

106 Diamond nanoparticles (DNP) were obtained from SkySpring Nanomaterials
107 (Product 0512HZ, nominal diameter 4-15 nm, www.ssnano.com), Inc (Houston, Tx).
108 Molybdenum disulfide (99%), N-methyl pyrrolidone (NMP), dimethylformamide
109 (DMF), ethanol (EtOH), isopropyl alcohol (IPA), methanol, dichloromethane,
110 triethylamine, dopamine, ascorbic acid, epinephrine, lithium tetrahydridoaluminate,
111 potassium ferrocyanide, potassium ferricyanide, potassium cyanide, and potassium
112 chloride were obtained from Aldrich Chemical Co (www.sigmaaldrich.com). 2,2-di-n-
113 propylacetic acid and *N,N,N*-trimethylferrocenylmethyl-amonium iodide were obtained
114 from Alfa Aesar (www.alfa.com/es). Sodium phosphate (www.merck.com) was
115 employed for the preparation of buffers. Water was purified with a Millipore Milli-Q-
116 System (www.millipore.com). All solutions were prepared just prior to use.

117

118

119 **Experimental techniques**

120 The AFM measurements were performed in air with Nanoscope IIIa (Veeco,
121 www.veeco.com) and Agilent 5500 (Agilent, www.agilent.com) systems. The images
122 were taken in the dynamic mode using silicon cantilevers (Bruker, www.bruker.com)
123 with a nominal force constant of 40 N/m and a nominal radius of 8 nm. First, large areas
124 (around 100 μm^2) were scanned in order to locate the MoS₂ flakes, which were then
125 imaged at higher resolution. The images, 1024 x 1024 pixels, were taken with different
126 cantilevers in order to ensure that the imaged structures were not due to tip artefacts.
127 Also, eventually imaging under liquid conditions was performed in order to discard
128 artefacts coming from remaining water used in the sample preparation. Supports used
129 were Si substrates from University Wafer (www.universitywafer.com, USA).

130 Impedance and voltammetric studies were carried out with an Ecochemie Autolab
131 PGSTAT302 N system (Utrecht, The Netherlands, www.ecochemie.nl) in a cell with a
132 working GC electrode (3 mm internal diameter) and a platinum wire as counter
133 electrode (www.metrohm.com). All potentials were reported with respect to a Ag/AgCl
134 reference electrode. DPV measurements were carried out in a 0.1 M phosphate buffer
135 (pH = 7) containing VA-Fc, with the following conditions: range potential from -50 mV
136 to 450 mV, scan rate 10 mVs⁻¹, pulse amplitude 60 mV and step potential 1 mV. EIS
137 experiments were performed in a 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH = 7), containing 10 mM
138 K₃Fe(CN)₆/ K₄Fe(CN)₆. A sinusoidal potential modulation of ± 10 mV amplitude in the
139 10⁵ Hz-10⁻² Hz frequency range, spaced logarithmically (120 per 8 decades), was
140 superimposed onto the formal potential of the redox couple, [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-}.

141 HPLC measurements were performed with a Jasco Analytica PU-1580 high pressure
142 pumping system, equipped with Rheodyne Model 7125 injector with a 20 μL loop and a

143 Kromasil C18 column (150 x 4.6 mm; 5 μ m; Scharlau). A Perkin Elmer 785A UV/VIS
144 was employed as detector at λ = 260 nm.

145

146 **Functionalization of valproic acid with aminoethyl-substituted ferrocene**

147 Organometallic compound $\text{Fe}\{[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_4)(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NHC(O)CH}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2](\eta^5\text{-}$
148 $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\}$ (VA-Fc) was synthesized by direct amide coupling of equimolar amounts of β -
149 aminoethylferrocene $\text{Fe}\{(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NH}_2)(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\}$ (500 mg, 2.18 mmol) with
150 2,2-di-n-propylacetic acid, in dry CH_2Cl_2 , in the presence of triethylamine. The solution
151 was concentrated and the solid formed was separated by filtration and dried under
152 vacuum to afford the desired compound VA-Fc which was isolated as a yellow-orange
153 solid (yield: 53%). Data obtained from ^1H NMR, IR and MS (FB^+) confirm that VA-Fc
154 has been successfully synthesized (data not shown).

155 Compound $\text{Fe}\{(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NH}_2)(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\}$ [48, 49] was selected as starting
156 metallocene since the reactive NH_2 functionality is separated from the cyclopentadienyl
157 ring by a two methylene flexible bridge. This fact is of importance because it minimizes
158 steric and electronic effects of the organometallic ferrocene moiety. The use of a β -
159 functionalized metallocene, in addition, avoids the instability of α -functional ferrocene
160 derivatives resulting from the stability of the α -ferrocenyl carbonium ion.

161 Concerning monofunctionalized ferrocene $\text{Fe}\{(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NH}_2)(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\}$ this
162 compound was prepared in two steps from *N,N,N*-trimethylferrocenylmethyl-amonium
163 iodide as starting material by adapting the literature procedures [50]. Firstly, $[(\eta^5\text{-}$
164 $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Fe}\{\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_4\}\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_3]\text{I}$ was reacted with potassium cyanide thus resulting 1-
165 cyanomethylferrocene which was isolated as a yellow crystalline solid in 63% yield.
166 The cyanomethylferrocene was converted into β -aminoethylferrocene by reduction with
167 LiAlH_4 followed by treatment with aqueous sodium hydroxide. After aqueous workup

168 and distillation in vacuum, primary amine $\text{Fe}\{(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NH}_2)(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\}$ was
169 obtained as an amber-brown oil in 66% yield.

170 VA-Fc was dissolved in methanol, giving rise to a $2.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ M VA-Fc stock solution.
171 Working solutions were prepared by dilution of the stock solution in phosphate buffer
172 0.1 M pH=7.0.

173

174 **Synthesis of MoS₂ platelets**

175 MoS₂ nano-sized powders were employed as starting materials to obtain MoS₂
176 atomic layers following a liquid exfoliation strategy [4], with some modifications. The
177 solvents selected as exfoliation mediums were NMP, DMF, EtOH/water (45:55) and
178 IPA/water (45:55). Briefly, 75 mg of the commercial MoS₂ powder was mixed with
179 10.0 mL of the corresponding solvent. After sonication of each dispersion for 2 hours, it
180 was kept at 4 °C during 24 hours and then centrifuged (1500 rpm, 45 minutes). The
181 supernatant was collected and subsequently employed for electrode modification.

182

183 **Preparation of the samples for AFM measurements**

184 Samples for AFM measurements were prepared by modifying Si surfaces as follows:
185 i) placing 6 μL of MoS₂ exfoliated in EtOH/water, ii) leaving air-dry and iii) depositing
186 6 μL of DNP dispersed in water (1 mg mL⁻¹). An additional sample was prepared in the
187 same way but employing DNP diluted 1:1000 with water (1 μg mL⁻¹).

188

189 **Preparation of the electrochemical sensors. Evaluation of the response.**

190 GC electrodes were polished with 1 μm diamond paste (Buehler) and rinsed with
191 water. Subsequently, four different sensors were obtained by modifying these GC
192 electrodes as follows: i) placing 6 μL of MoS₂ exfoliated in NMP, DMF, EtOH/water or

193 IPA/water solvent, ii) leaving air-dry, iii) depositing 6 μL of DNP dispersed in water (1
194 mg mL^{-1}) and air-dry again. For comparison, four other electrochemical sensors
195 consisting in a first layer of DNP and a second layer of MoS_2 (exfoliated in NMP,
196 DMF, EtOH/water or IPA/water) were also prepared following the same procedure but
197 inverting the order of MoS_2 and DNP deposition.

198 Sensors containing only MoS_2 or DNP were obtained by modifying the GC electrode
199 with 6 μL of the corresponding nanomaterial and leaving air-dry it.

200 The sensor response was evaluated as follows: the electrodes, modified as described
201 above, were introduced into an electrochemical cell containing 3.5 μM of VA-Fc in 0.1
202 M phosphate buffer (pH = 7) and the differential pulse voltammograms were obtained
203 (see DPV conditions in the experimental techniques section). The calibration curve was
204 obtained: i) recording DPVs for different VA-Fc concentrations in the range potential
205 from -50 mV to 450 mV, ii) plotting the intensity current obtained at +0.18 V towards
206 the corresponding VA-Fc concentration.

207

208 **Evaluation of the method: VA-Fc analysis in serum samples.**

209 Human blood was centrifuged at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min at 2500 rpm. The serum was then
210 separated with a syringe and stored at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ prior to analysis. Samples were diluted 1:100
211 with phosphate buffer (pH 7) and spiked with five different VA-Fc concentrations (from
212 $1.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M to $5.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M). The determination was carried out by the DPV method in
213 order to calculate the recoveries.

214 HPLC-UV measurements were performed for comparison. Chromatograms were
215 obtained at a flow rate of 1.0 mL min^{-1} , employing EtOH/ NaH_2PO_4 0.01 M (60:40, v/v)
216 as mobile phase, pH 6. A wavelength of 260 nm was employed for detection. Serum
217 samples were diluted 1:100 in mobile phase and spiked to obtain final VA-Fc

218 concentrations of $1.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $2.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $5.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M. Samples were filtered through a 0.45
219 μm pore size nylon filter.

220

221 **Results and discussion**

222 We have developed an electrochemical sensor by combining two nanomaterials,
223 DNP and MoS_2 , which are attracting an emerging attention in the sensors field. As
224 mentioned in the introduction, several (bio)sensors have been developed using one of
225 these two nanomaterials, leading to improved performances. Thus, their excellent
226 individual properties suggest the possibility of giving rise to a synergistic effect when
227 employed together. In particular, the presence of DNP can overcome one of the main
228 drawbacks of employing MoS_2 in electrochemical sensors, related to its low
229 conductivity. Until now, hybrids formed by MoS_2 and different nanomaterials such as
230 graphene or carbon nanotubes have been assayed as sensor platforms, but DNP have not
231 been tested for this goal.

232

233 **Optimization of the sensor construction**

234 Following the procedure described in the experimental section, we have exfoliated
235 molybdenum disulfide by sonication in four different solvents to produce stable MoS_2
236 dispersions sheets. In order to evaluate the suitability of a given solvent, we have
237 obtained the response of four different sensors fabricated by modifying GC electrodes
238 with DNP and MoS_2 previously exfoliated in NMP, DMF, EtOH/ H_2O and IPA/ H_2O ,
239 respectively. The differential pulse voltammograms, displayed in Figure 1, are obtained
240 in a 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH=7.0, containing $3.5 \mu\text{M}$ of VA-Fc. Although a well-
241 defined oxidation peak, corresponding to VA-Fc, is observed for all cases, the response
242 is clearly better when EtOH/ H_2O is employed as solvent. In particular, the peak current

243 measured at a potential of +0.18 V is approximately three times higher in comparison to
244 the current obtained for the rest of solvents.

245

246 **Figure 1.** DPV response of GC electrodes modified with DNP and MoS₂ in a 0.1 M
247 phosphate buffer pH=7.0, containing 3.5 μM of VA-Fc. MoS₂ employed for the sensors
248 fabrication had been previously exfoliated employing as solvent: (a) NMP, (b) DMF, (c)
249 IPA/water and (d) EtOH/water. DPV conditions: range potential from -50 mV to 450
250 mV, scan rate 10 mV s⁻¹, pulse amplitude 60 mV and step potential 1 mV.

251

252 Once EtOH/H₂O was selected as solvent, we proceeded to optimize the modification
253 procedure. In order to do this, two different sensor configurations have been compared.
254 The first one corresponds to that described until now, a first layer of MoS₂ in direct
255 contact with the GC surface, and a second layer of DNP in contact with the medium.
256 The response of this sensor (GC/MoS₂/DNP) has been previously shown (Figure 1,
257 curve d). The second configuration is just the opposite, an inner DNP layer in contact
258 with the electrode and an outer MoS₂ layer. The response obtained with this
259 configuration (GC/DNP/MoS₂) is similar or even higher (data not shown), than that
260 corresponding to GC/MoS₂/DNP. However, this sensor arrangement was discarded due
261 to its poor stability. In particular, the DPV measured after 3 days is similar to that
262 obtained for the GC/DNP system, suggesting that the MoS₂ layer is partially lost when

263 it is directly exposed to the medium. When this layer is protected by DNP the stability
264 sensor is highly improved as it will be discussed later.

265 Finally, some experimental conditions, such as pH, electrolyte and pulse amplitude
266 in DPV measurements were optimized. In particular, the response of a GC/MoS₂/DNP
267 electrode was obtained in the following electrolytes, containing 3.5 μM of VA-Fc:
268 acetate buffer at pH=4.0, phosphate buffer at pH=7.0 and borate buffer at pH=10.0.
269 Concerning pulse amplitude, values in the range 10-80 mV were assayed. The best
270 results were obtained for phosphate buffer at pH 7.0 and a pulse amplitude of 60 mV.

271

272 **Morphological sensor characterization: AFM measurements**

273 The different steps of the sensor construction were characterized by atomic force
274 microscopy (AFM). Figure 2A shows a 5 x 5 μm² image in which several MoS₂
275 platelets can be observed. They have a height in the 4-6 nm range. Their size varies
276 from few nm² to areas above 1 μm². This sample in fact corresponds to a MoS₂ sample
277 on which DNP (from a diluted stock, 1 μg mL⁻¹) were deposited (see the experimental
278 section). It can be distinguished how these DNP are deposited, mainly as aggregates, on
279 top of the large MoS₂ platelets. When the background of the image is inspected in
280 detail, a small structure can be discerned. When this zone is imaged at higher resolution,
281 images as that of Figure 2B are obtained. Here, small plateaus are observed with
282 relatively jagged perimeters and lateral sizes below 200 nm. From the height
283 distribution of the image (Figure 2C) it is clearly obtained that the average measured
284 height of these flakes is close to 0.8 nm, i.e., very close (within the error bar) to that of a
285 MoS₂ monolayer. It should be noted that, in this height histogram, we have taken the
286 zero height value at the lowest point of the whole image and not at the average height of
287 the flat background (which is located in the histogram at 0.6 nm). Thus, the MoS₂

288 thickness is the height difference, along the x-axis of the histogram, between both
289 peaks. In Figure 2D is displayed an image taken on a sample prepared by using the
290 same concentration of both the DNP and MoS₂ employed in the samples characterized
291 electrochemically. In particular, now, the DNP number is considerably higher than in
292 Figure 2A since a DNP stock of 1 mg mL⁻¹ was employed for modification.
293 Notwithstanding, once more rather flat platelets are imaged with heights in the 3-5 nm
294 range. However, most of them are almost totally covered by DNP (for instance the large
295 one at the top left corner of the image) while others (as that at the top right corner and
296 the one close to the center of the image) have only some DNP on their surface. The
297 DNP height is in the 5-15 nm range. Interestingly, they tend to aggregate on these
298 partially DNP-covered MoS₂ flakes mainly at their perimeter, i.e., at the steps. In
299 contrast with Figure 2A, now the DNP are also found on the substrate, outside the MoS₂
300 flakes, which is likely due to their high amount. Finally, in Figure 2E is displayed a
301 zoom of one of these partially DNP-covered MoS₂ flakes. This flake has a thickness
302 close to 5.5 nm and the DNP on top are 8-15 nm high. At given spots, mostly at the
303 perimeter of the flake, aggregation of DNP is observed.

304

305 **Figure 2.** (A) AFM image of SiO₂ substrates modified with MoS₂ and DNP for a low
 306 DNP concentration. (B) High resolution image of the flat background revealing the
 307 presence of small MoS₂ flakes. Its corresponding height distribution is shown in (C).
 308 Note that we have taken the zero height value at the lowest point of the whole image.
 309 (D) AFM image of SiO₂ substrates modified with MoS₂ and DNP nanostructures for a
 310 high DNP concentration. (E) Detail of a MoS₂ flake partially covered by DNP. The
 311 horizontal bars indicate (A) 2 μm, (B) 500 nm, (D) 3 μm and (E) 500 nm, respectively.
 312 Note that (B) and (E) are not zoomed regions of (A) and (D), respectively but rather
 313 higher resolution images taken on similar zones of the sample.

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Evaluation of the MoS₂ and DNP synergetic effect in electrochemical sensing

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In order to evaluate the synergetic effect of both nanomaterials, the response of the GC/MoS₂/DNP sensor was compared to that of sensors containing only one of the nanostructures, DNP or MoS₂. Figure 3 shows the differential pulse voltammograms of bare GC, GC/MoS₂, GC/DNP and GC/MoS₂/DNP systems. The oxidation peak, corresponding to VA-Fc, is observed for all cases, but its intensity current (measured at +0.18 V) depends on the specific electrode modification. Bare GC electrodes (curve a) and MoS₂-based sensors (curve b) lead to a similar intensity current response, lower than that corresponding to DNP-based ones (curve c). As displayed in curve d, the

325 simultaneous presence of MoS₂ and DNP gives rise to an intensity current response that
326 is nine and five times higher than that of GC/MoS₂ and GC/DNP, respectively. This
327 result indicates that employing MoS₂ and DNP together as sensing elements allows the
328 development of electrochemical sensors with an enhanced performance. Although we
329 have only tested it in the particular case of VA-Fc determination, this promising starting
330 point suggests the possibility of a broad applicability for determination of other
331 analytes.

332

333 **Figure 3.** DPV response of (a) bare GC, (b) GC/MoS₂, (c) GC/DNP and (d)
334 GC/MoS₂/DNP electrodes in a 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH=7.0, containing 3.5 μM of
335 VA-Fc. MoS₂ employed for the sensor fabrication has been previously exfoliated
336 employing as solvent EtOH/water. DPV conditions: range potential from -50 mV to 450
337 mV, scan rate 10 mV s⁻¹, pulse amplitude 60 mV and step potential 1 mV.

338

339

340 The improved response obtained for the sensor containing both nanomaterials is likely
341 due to an increase of both the effective surface area of the electrode and the efficiency
342 in the charge transfer caused by the concomitant presence of MoS₂ and DNP. In order to
343 confirm the latter point, the interfacial properties of bare and modified glassy carbon
344 electrodes were studied by EIS. Figure 4 displays the Nyquist diagrams for GC,

345 GC/MoS₂, GC/DNP and GC/MoS₂/DNP systems. The semicircles correspond to the
 346 charge transfer resistance (R_{CT}) limiting process that is associated with the
 347 surface/electrolyte interface. The linear part corresponds to the diffusion-controlled
 348 process.

349
 350 **Figure 4.** Nyquist plots of (a) bare GC, (b) GC/MoS₂, (c) GC/DNP and (d)
 351 GC/MoS₂/DNP electrodes obtained in a 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH = 7) containing 10
 352 mM [Fe (CN)₆]^{3-/4-} by applying a sinusoidal potential modulation with amplitude of
 353 ±10 mV over the frequency range 10⁵ Hz-10⁻² Hz. Inset: Randles electrical equivalent
 354 circuit.

356 The impedance diagrams were fitted considering the Randles electrical equivalent
 357 circuit, shown in the inset of Figure 4, where R_s , R_{CT} , C_{dl} and Z_w are the electrolyte
 358 resistance, the charge transfer resistance, the double layer capacitance and the Warburg
 359 impedance, respectively. From the fit, R_{CT} values of 4536.4 Ω and 9000 Ω were
 360 obtained for GC and GC/MoS₂, respectively. Upon modification of the GC surface with
 361 MoS₂ (curve b), it results an increase of the charge transfer resistance value with respect
 362 to the bare GC electrode (curve a). This fact suggests that MoS₂ hinders the electron
 363 transfer between the redox probe, [Fe (CN)₆]^{3-/4-} and the glassy carbon electrode. In
 364 contrast, for both the GC/DNP and the GC/MoS₂/DNP systems, just a straight line with

365 a slope close to 1 (0.94 and 0.93, respectively) is obtained (curves c and d). Therefore,
366 the presence of DNP in the surface clearly improves the charge transfer, being a
367 diffusion-limited transport process observed. This behavior confirms that MoS₂/DNP
368 hybrid structures improve the electron transfer with respect to a MoS₂ modified surface,
369 rendering it very attractive for electrochemical sensors development.

370 On the other hand, the electrochemical surface area was determined by recording five
371 consecutive cyclic voltamograms at 50 mVs⁻¹ with the different modified electrodes in
372 a KCl 1M solution containing 5.0 mM K₄[Fe(CN)₆] / K₃[Fe(CN)₆]. The mean measured
373 peak current (I_p) is related with the electrochemical surface area (A) through the
374 Randles-Sevick equation:

$$375 \quad I_{pa} = (2.69 \times 10^5) n^{3/2} A D^{1/2} v^{1/2} C$$

376 where v is the scan rate, n the number of electrons, D the diffusion coefficient (6.5 10⁻⁶
377 cm² s⁻¹ at 20 °C [51]) and C the concentration of the redox compound. Electrochemical
378 surface areas of (0.065 ± 0.004) cm², (0.0784 ± 0.0005) cm² and (0.0896 ± 0.0003) cm²
379 were obtained for GC, GC/DNP and GC/MoS₂/DNP electrodes, respectively. These
380 values confirm that the presence of both nanomaterials results in a considerable increase
381 of the effective area.

382

383 **Response of the GC/MoS₂/DNP sensor towards increasing VA-Fc concentration**

384 Once the synergetic effect of MoS₂ and DNP has been assessed, DPVs of
385 GC/MoS₂/DNP at increasing VA-Fc concentration were recorded (Figure S1). The
386 current measured at a potential of +0.18 V was plotted as a function of the VA-Fc
387 concentration in solution (data not shown), being linear in the range from 9.0 10⁻⁷ M to
388 5.5 10⁻⁶ M, according to the following equation $I \text{ (A)} = 7 \cdot 10^{-8} (\pm 3 \cdot 10^{-8}) + 0.74 (\pm 0.01) C$
389 (M), with a correlation coefficient of 0.990. The sensitivity, calculated as the slope of

390 the calibration curve, was 0.74 A M^{-1} ($8.26 \text{ A M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, when normalized to the
391 electrochemical area). The detection and quantification limits, obtained as the ratio
392 between three and ten times the standard deviation of the blank signal and the
393 sensitivity, were $2.7 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ M}$ and $9.0 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ M}$, respectively. As can be observed in Table
394 S1, the detection limit is similar or even better than those obtained by others methods
395 commonly employed for VA determination [35-47]. Note that some of the analytical
396 techniques reported in the literature require the derivatization of VA. For example, for
397 optical detection, derivatization with a chromophore/fluorophore is usually performed
398 in an attempt of improving sensitivity, given the poor valproic acid UV absorption
399 capacity. In our case, for electrochemical detection, derivatization with a suitable redox
400 group is also needed, in order to obtain a redox response at around $+0.2 \text{ V}$, which
401 minimize the potential interferences. From the point of view of derivatization, our
402 method does not represent an improvement with respect to the other techniques usually
403 employed, such as HPLC or GC-MS, but it is less expensive and less time consuming,
404 requiring also less sophisticated equipments.

405 Finally, reproducibility and stability were evaluated. Reproducibility was estimated
406 by measuring $2.2 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ M}$ of VA-Fc with parallel GC/MoS₂/DNP sensors. A relative
407 standard deviation value (RSD) of 8% is obtained for five different measurements
408 ($n=5$). Concerning operational stability, a RSD value of 6% was obtained for 50
409 consecutive measurements with the same GC/MoS₂/DNP sensor. Storage stability was
410 also studied by recording DPVs of a GC/MoS₂/DNP sensor every 15 days. The sensor
411 was kept at $4 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ between measurements. Even after 45 days, 99 % of the original
412 response was retained, indicating an excellent stability.

413 In order to evaluate the selectivity, the influence of several potential interferences on
414 the sensor response was studied. In this sense, we have obtained the sensor response

415 before and after adding increasing amounts of dopamine, ascorbic acid and epinephrine
416 to a solution containing $1.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M of VA-Fc. It was considered that each compound
417 interferes at a concentration level enough to produce a variation of 10% in the initial
418 response. According to this, the presence of epinephrine, ascorbic acid and dopamine in
419 the sample interferes for concentrations of $5.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M, $2.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M, and $1.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M,
420 respectively. Note that the interference concentration level for all the compounds
421 assayed ranges from 2 to 5 times higher than the VA-Fc concentration in solution.

422

423 **Analytical application in real samples: determination of VA-Fc in serum**

424 The applicability of the sensor was tested for VA-Fc determination in serum samples.
425 As mentioned in the experimental section, human blood was centrifuged at 4 °C for 10
426 min at 2500 rpm. The serum was then separated with a syringe and stored at 4 °C prior
427 to analysis. Samples were diluted 1:100 with phosphate buffer pH 7.0 and spiked with
428 five different VA-Fc concentrations (from $1.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M to $5.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M). Dilution 1:100
429 allows obtaining a final concentration that both corresponds with possible physiological
430 concentrations and fits in the linear range of the sensors. The VA-Fc determination was
431 carried out by the DPV method (see experimental section). The recoveries, obtained for
432 each VA-Fc concentration assayed, are summarized in Table 1. The recoveries were
433 from 96% to 111%, indicating that the sensor can be successfully used to detect VA-Fc.

434

[VA-Fc] added (M)	[VA-Fc] found (M)	Recovery (%)
$1.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$	111
$2.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	106
$3.9 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$4.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	106
$5.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	96

435 **Table 1.** Recoveries of VA-Fc from spiked serum samples

436

437 For evaluating the feasibility of the electrochemical method, serum samples were
438 also analyzed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC-UV) technique.
439 Chromatographic conditions were selected according to reference 52 (see experimental
440 section). Under these conditions, retention time of VA-Fc was 13.3 minutes. From the
441 analysis of VA-Fc solutions of increasing concentrations, a good linearity of the
442 calibration graph is obtained: $A = -1854 (\pm 7) + 179 (\pm 8) \times 10^7 C (M)$; $r = 0.999$. As
443 described in experimental section, three different samples (spiked to obtain final VA-Fc
444 concentrations of 1.0×10^{-5} , 2.5×10^{-5} and 5.0×10^{-5} M) were injected in the chromatographic
445 system. Recoveries of 93%, 84% and 81%, respectively were obtained, demonstrating
446 that similar recoveries are obtained by both methods.

447

448 **4. Conclusions**

449 In the present study, we have developed the first electrochemical sensor based on the
450 combined employment of MoS₂ nanosheets and DNP as sensing elements and we have
451 proved its applicability for determination of valproic acid previously derivatized with a
452 ferrocene group. The best results were obtained for sensors developed employing MoS₂
453 dispersed in EtOH/water with a configuration consisting in a first layer of MoS₂ and a
454 second layer of DNP. Concerning the morphology of the sensor surface, rather flat
455 MoS₂ platelets are observed by AFM, being most of them almost totally covered by
456 DNP. The presence of DNP significantly decreases the resistance charge transfer of the
457 sensor surface compared to MoS₂. We prove that the combination of MoS₂ and DNP led
458 to sensors with an enhanced analytical performance towards the oxidation of VA-Fc in
459 comparison with sensors containing only one of the nanomaterials. Since an important
460 synergistic effect takes place, the combination of these both emergent nanomaterials can
461 offer new opportunities to develop electrochemical sensors with improved performances

462 for detection of different analytes, suggesting the possibility of a broad applicability. In
463 our case, since valproic acid is not electroactive, its derivatization with a redox group is
464 needed as previous step.

465

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Synergistic effect of MoS₂ and diamond nanoparticles in electrochemical sensors: determination of an anticonvulsant drug

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Figure S1. DPVs of GC/MoS₂/DNP sensor in a 0.1 M pH=7.0 phosphate buffer, containing increasing VA-Fc concentration: a) $5.5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ M, b) $1.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M, c) $2.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M, d) $3.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M and e) $3.9 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M. DPV conditions: range potential from -50 mV to 450 mV, scan rate 10 mV s^{-1} , pulse amplitude 60 mV and step potential 1 mV.

Table S1. Comparison of detection limits of valproic acid obtained by different methods

REFERENCE	METHOD / MATERIALS USED	DERIVATIZATION REAGENT	DETECTION LIMIT (µg/mL)
[35]	GC-MS	-----	1
[36]	LC-MS and CID-MS/MS	-----	0.31
[37]	RP-HPLC	Arylamide N-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-2-propylpentanamide	0.128
[38]	HPLC	2-bromo-2'-acetonaphnone	0.01
[39]	UPLC-MS/MS	2-picolyamine	0.03
[40]	HPLC-UV	2,4'-dibromoacetophenone	5
[41]	HPLC-MS/MS	4-dimethylaminobenzylamine dihydrochloride	0.2
[42]	HS-LPME-GC	-----	0.8
[43]	Capillary electrophoresis	-----	0.08
[44]	Electrochemical sensor (APTES-MNPs/PGE)	-----	0.4
[45]	Nanomechanical biosensor	-----	45
[46]	Proton sensor/Fluorescent detection (TGA-CdTe QDs)	-----	0.24
[47]	Potentiometric sensor- SIA (Mn(III)TPP-Cl/ MTES)	-----	130
Present work	Electrochemical sensor (GC/MoS ₂ /DNP)	Ferrocene	0.096

GC-MS (gas chromatography-mass spectrometry), LC-MS (liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry), CID-MS/MS (low-energy collision induced dissociation tandem mass spectrometry), RP-HPLC (reversed-phase high performance liquid chromatography), UPLC (ultraperformance liquid chromatography), HPLC-UV (high performance liquid chromatography-ultraviolet), HS-LPME-GC (headspace liquid phase microextraction-gas chromatography), APTES-MNPs (3-aminopropyletriethoxy silane coated magnetic nanoparticles), PGE (pencil graphite surface), TGA-CdTe QDs (thioglycolic acid -capped CdTe quantum dots), SIA (sequential-injection analysis system), Mn(III)TPP-Cl (Manganese (III) tetraphenylporphyrin), MTES (methyltriethoxysilane sol-gel), GC (Glassy carbon electrode), DNP (diamond nanoparticles).